

1 Errata for PhD Thesis:

Integrating User eXperience Principles and Practices into Software Development Organizations: An Empirical Investigation

Pariya Hajar Kashfi

- On page 11, second paragraph, third from the last row: change Gird to Grid
- On page 48, first paragraph, change Gird to Grid
- On page 94, second paragraph, third from the last row: change “gird” to “grid”
- On page 139, 10th from last row: change “we found that” to “we found the importance of”
- On page 147, last paragraph: change “principles GT” to “priciples of GT”
- On page 158, section 4.3, change the sub-title “Challenges...” to “4.3.1 Challenges...”
- On page 161, first quotation box: change “when it comes” to “when it comes to”
- On page 162, change the sub-title “4.3.1 Challenges...” to “4.3.2 Challenges...”
- On page 165, change the sub-title “4.3.2 Challenges...” to “4.3.3 Challenges...”
- On page 200, second paragraph from last, change XU to UX
- **Due to compile issues, the reference numbers and bibliography of the attached papers are not reliable. The reader ,therefore, is encouraged to use the following individual bibliography errata for each attached paper**

2 Bibliography Errata for paper I

- On page 11, first paragraph: change [28,28,66] to [13,28,66]
- On page 52, second paragraph: change [39] to [38]
- On page 75, row 2: change [36] to [43]

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3 Bibliography Errata for paper II

- On page 88, last paragraph: change [11] to [10]
- On page 91, footnote 1: change [15] to [14]

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4 Bibliography Errata for paper III

- On page 102, first paragraph: change [1,~~8~~9] to [1,8]
- On page 102, second paragraph: change [3,~~9~~,21] to [3,21,~~5~~8]
- On page 102, second paragraph: change [11,17,~~18~~] to [11,17,~~30~~]
- On page 102, third paragraph: change [~~20~~,21] to [21,~~24~~]
- On page 102, third paragraph: change [18,20,~~26~~,32] to [18,20,~~27~~,32]
- On page 102, third paragraph: change [11,18,20,26,~~26~~,32,65] to [11,18,20,26,~~27~~,32,65]
- On page 103, second paragraph: change [10,~~11~~] to [10,~~12~~]
- On page 103, last paragraph: change [34-36] to [~~33~~,34,36]
- On page 127, second paragraph: change [26,~~64~~] to [26,~~68~~]
- On page 127, third paragraph: change [~~11~~,54,56] to [54,56,~~57~~]
- On page 130, first paragraph: change [~~60~~,61] to [~~70~~,71]
- On page 130, second paragraph: change [42] to [69]

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5 Bibliography Errata for paper IV

- On page 140, second paragraph: change [10,11] to [10,12]
- On page 140, third paragraph: change [14-16] to [14,19,20]
- On page 141, fourth paragraph: change [29] to [39]
- On page 142, second paragraph: change [16,17,26-28,87] to [17,19,27,41,45,87]
- On page 142, fifth paragraph: change [31] to [51]
- On page 142, fifth paragraph: change [33] to [53]
- On page 143, first paragraph: change “Winter et al. [11]” to “Winter et al. [9]”
- On page 143, third paragraph: change [11,16,40,86] to [9,16,40,86]
- On page 143, third paragraph: change [11,11,16,22] to [9,11,16,22]
- On page 173, second paragraph: change [31,35] to [35,51]

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7 Bibliography Errata for paper VI

- On page 192, second paragraph: change [8,11] to [8,10]
- On page 192, third paragraph, fifth row: change “Stakeholder roles [5]” to “Stakeholder roles [4]”
- On page 196, first paragraph: change [18] to [17]
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